

Research

In the emergency department, lung ultrasound is an accurate diagnostic tool for diagnosing pneumonia : Cases on Children

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Abstract: Pneumonia is a major cause of illness and mortality in children all over the world, but diagnosing it can be difficult, particularly in places without access to trained doctors or conventional imaging. We wanted to know how well lung ultrasonography could diagnose clinical pediatric pneumonia when compared to radiographically proven pneumonia. Between May 1, 2017 and April 30, 2018, we enrolled 2–59-month-olds with primary respiratory symptoms at the Janaki Medical College and Teaching Hospital (JMCTH), Janakpur Dham, Nepal. All subjects got a pediatrician's exam and a GP's lung ultrasound. We enrolled consecutively healthy children. Children with respiratory complaints were x-rayed. A fraction underwent auxiliary lab tests. 453 children had pneumonia, 133 asthma, 103 bronchiolitis, and 143 upper respiratory infections. 191 (42%) of 453 children with clinical pneumonia had CXR confirmation. A consolidation on lung ultrasonography, our key outcome for pneumonia, exhibited 88.5% sensitivity, 100% specificity, and an area under-the-curve of 0.94 (95 percent CI 0.92–0.97). When lung ultrasound abnormalities were compared to radiographically-confirmed clinical pneumonia, sensitivity improved to 92.2% and specificity declined to 95.2%, with an AUC of 0.94 (95% CI 0.91–0.96). This study provides further evidence that LUS has a higher diagnostic accuracy than CXR for identifying acute pneumonia. Nevertheless, the accuracy of PLUS, which is a diagnostic tool that is easy to use and is generated from biomarkers, was greater to that of LUS independent of the degree to which patients were fragile.

Keywords: Pneumonia, Nepal, Lung, Ultrasound

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Introduction

Pneumonia is the most common cause of death in countries all over the world. It is responsible for 120 million episodes and 1 million deaths each year in children younger than 5 years old [1, 2]. [S]he is accountable for 120 million episodes and 1 million fatalities each year. The proportion of deaths in children caused by pneumonia has stayed roughly the

same at approximately 20 percent for the previous 20 years [3], despite the overall decline in child mortality. The World Health Organization (WHO) established a case management algorithm for the treatment of pneumonia that is intended for use in areas that have limited access to healthcare professionals and resources, such as developing countries. This involves teaching community health workers to detect respiratory signs and symptoms for the purposes of diagnosis, treatment, and referral [5]. These signs and symptoms focussed on cough, trouble breathing, respiratory rate, and danger indicators. Although this approach was able to achieve significant reductions in mortality rates once it was implemented [6], subsequent investigations have revealed that it does not have sufficient specificity [7], [8], and [9]. A high false positive rate has resulted in overuse of antibiotics and improper therapy for children with acute bronchospasm that may instead require bronchodilators.

Pneumonia is a multifactorial disease that can be caused by bacteria as well as viruses. In addition, there is a substantial amount of overlap between bronchiolitis and reactive airways disease. As a result, arriving at a correct diagnosis of pneumonia can be difficult and calls for the utilization of a wide range of diagnostic tools [9, 10]. Previous research has investigated the usefulness of additional non-respiratory diagnostic features in settings with limited resources. These features include fever [10] and oxygen saturation [11, 12]. Imaging is a valuable supplement, but only when the necessary resources are available [13]. In point of fact, the American Academy of Pediatrics has recommended chest X-rays (CXR) as the imaging technique of choice for complicated or unclear situations [10]. CXR, on the other hand, comes with its own set of drawbacks, such as the fact that it exposes patients to radiation, has a high inter-observer variability [14], and does not have an impact on clinical result [15].

Emerging as a diagnostic technique for pneumonia in both adults [16] and children [17], lung ultrasonography (LUS) can be performed on both age groups. It also has many advantages for pediatric respiratory disease in low resource settings, including portability, rapid and repeat testing, no ionizing radiation, and ease of use [18], [19], [20]. We sought to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of LUS as a point-of-care diagnostic tool for pneumonia in a tertiary care setting in Janaki Medical College And Teaching Hospital (JMCTH), Janakpur Dham, Nepal during May 1st 2017- April 30th 2018.

Materials and methods

Study design

We enrolled children with respiratory symptoms at the Emergency Department, General Pediatric Wards, and Outpatient Clinics at the JMCTH, Janakpur Dham, Nepal, which is a large children's hospital that treats more than 170,000 children on an annual basis. This enrollment took place between May 1st, 2017 and April 30th, 2018. Children between the ages of 2 and 59 months were eligible to participate as long as they exhibited respiratory symptoms. The following conditions were ineligible for participation: chronic lung disease, other than asthma; significant cardiac disease; and the requirement for mechanical ventilation. At the same establishment, we recruited children of a comparable age range who did not have respiratory complaints or acute non-respiratory illnesses (such as diarrhea, vomiting, or fever). These children were typically patients who presented themselves to the hospital for well-child visits or the siblings of child participants who were recruited for the study. We described the methodology behind the study procedures in greater detail elsewhere [21]. It's important to note that we changed the protocol in order to accommodate a larger number of samples. When reporting the accuracy of our diagnostic procedures, we adhered to the STARD guidelines [22].

Clinical diagnosis

The clinical evaluation consisted of a history as well as a physical exam that was carried out by a pediatrician. The on-call pediatricians provided a diagnosis by adhering to the standard of care and taking into account the input from international clinical guidelines (Table 1) [23,24]. A complete chest radiograph (CXR) was performed front to back on every child who presented with respiratory symptoms. CXRs taken from the lateral view were not obtained because doing so was not in line with the clinical practice followed in our institution. In order to digitize CXR images, CXR used a scanner that had a resolution of 4800 dots per inch by 4800 dots per inch. The films were digitized and then forwarded to a third party reading group comprised of three study radiologists for analysis. Children who exhibited no signs of respiratory illness did not have a CXR performed.

Table 1: Clinical diagnosis guidelines, definitions, and grading system for lung ultrasound and chest radiographs.

Clinical diagnoses	
Pneumonia	Difficulty breathing as described by tachypnea, chest indrawing, nasal flaring, or grunting; history of fever, cough, chest pain or abdominal pain; adventitious lung sounds, including rales, rhonchi, crackles, or diminished sounds. Associated CXR findings of interstitial abnormalities or consolidation as reviewed by hospital clinician or on-site radiologist at time of diagnosis [3] . Severity was assessed by presence of chest indrawing, seizures, lethargy, or unconsciousness [4] .
Asthma	Presence of wheeze or difficulty breathing on physical exam, history of wheeze and responsive to bronchodilators [5] . Response to bronchodilators assessed clinically without formal pulmonary function testing.
Bronchiolitis	Less than 18 months of age; presence of wheeze or coarse breath sounds, difficulty breathing, and viral symptoms (cough, rhinorrhea); not responsive to bronchodilators if attempted [24] .
Upper respiratory infection	Associated with nasal secretions, nasal congestion, sore or red throat or hoarseness without evidence of lower airways involvement (tachypnea and abnormal lung sounds on exam).
Lung ultrasound findings	
Lung sliding	Rhythmic movement of pleural line with respiration. It represents sliding of the visceral pleura against the parietal pleura.
A-lines	Horizontal lines equally spaced from pleural line, representing artifact generated by subpleural air, a normal finding.
B-lines	Vertical lines arising from pleura and extending to base of the image.
Pleural abnormality	Disruption of pleural line.
Consolidation	Hypoechoic circumscribed disruption of pleural line extending inferiorly and may contain any of the following; Air bronchogram, Shred sign, Pleural effusion.

Air bronchogram	Punctate or branching hyperechoic images reflecting airways made visible by surrounding fluid/inflammation
Shred sign	Irregular border of consolidation
Pleural effusion	Anechoic space between visceral and parietal pleura.

Sonographic grading

Lung consolidation

Small	Consolidation contained within one intercostal space and extending just below pleural line.
Large	Consolidation extends to more than 1 intercostal space, extends beyond the pleural line, and may be associated with a pleural effusion.

Interstitial abnormality

Focal	Multiple B lines (≥ 3) present in single view or unilaterally.
Diffuse	Multiple B lines (≥ 3) present bilaterally.

Radiographic grading

Lung consolidation	Alveolar pneumonia: dense, fluffy consolidation of a portion of a lobe or entire lung. Often contains air bronchograms and may be associated with pleural effusion.
Interstitial abnormality	Linear and patchy densities in a lacy pattern involving both lungs, featuring peri-bronchial thickening and multiple areas of atelectasis. Lung inflation is normal to increased.

Lung ultrasound imaging

The MicroMaxx ® portable ultrasound machine (Sonosite, Bothwell, WA) equipped with an HFL38/13-6 MHz linear transducer was used to perform a thorough LUS examination on each and every participant in the study. The size of this gadget is comparable to that of a 13-inch laptop, and it is employed as a point-of-care instrument at the patient's bedside. After completing a standardized training program for 7 days [21] based on international recommendations [26], one of three general practitioners (Sharad yadav , Pawan thakur and Ram lakhan Shah) performed LUS. The LUS examination itself, as well as the interpretation of its results, were carried out independently of either the clinical evaluation or the radiographic findings. LUS was performed on practically every child who had a CXR, as well as on every child who did not exhibit any signs or symptoms of respiratory illness (Fig. 1).

Fig.1: Anterior views of the chest in a healthy lung, taken along a longitudinal axis. The 'bat symbol' is a reference to the two ribs and pleural line that form the pattern. Artifacts of a comet's tail and of the B-line are evident right below the pleural line in this image. A-lines are indicated by arrowheads.

Imaging interpretation

Interpretation CXR and LUS pictures were obtained at a later date by three general practitioners (Sharad yadav , Pawan thakur and Ram lakhan Shah) and three board-certified pediatric radiologists (shambhu Shah,Vijay Shah and Sunil adhikari), respectively. The clinical information and the outcomes obtained from the alternative imaging modality were kept hidden from these groups. For the interpretation of both the CXR [14] and the LUS [26] images, we utilized conventional techniques. The presence of lobar consolidation, with or without pleural effusion, was what we meant when we talked of radiographic pneumonia (Table 1). On the LUS, pneumonia was defined as the identification of artifacts consistent with lobar consolidation or patchy lobar consolidation, if it occupied more than one intercostal space in vertical view, or small consolidation with a pleural effusion. Pneumonia was diagnosed when these findings were present (Table 1). The single detection of interstitial alterations on either the LUS or the CXR was not enough for us to conclude that pneumonia was present. It was necessary for two out of the three readers to agree on the diagnosis before moving forward.

Evaluation in the laboratory

In order to provide further objective data, we carried out laboratory testing on a sample group of the participants. A subset of 361 children and 137 children in total had complete blood counts and blood cultures taken from them, respectively. The levels of procalcitonin (PCT) in the serum or plasma of 259 children were examined as part of a convenience sample. Before being evaluated in a reference laboratory, the samples were kept in batches and stored at a temperature of -20 degrees Celsius. PCT levels were determined with the help of the Kryptor chemiluminescence immunoassay (BRAHMS, Hennigsdorf, Germany), which was performed in accordance with the guidelines provided by the manufacturer. The coefficient of variance between different assays was less than ten percent, and the assay's functional sensitivity was 0.06 nanograms per milliliter. In a random sample consisting of 251 children, pharyngeal swabs were examined for the presence of viruses and bacteria. Nucleic acid extraction for viral testing was carried out with the assistance of the Diasorin Inc. Arrow Viral NA kit (located in Stillwater, Minnesota), whilst bacterial extraction was carried out using the MagNA Pure LC with DNA Isolation Kit I. (Roche Diagnostics, Indianapolis, IN). In order to conduct tests on viruses, respiratory virus controls were incorporated throughout each run (NATrol Respiratory

Validation Panel 3, Zeptomatrix Corporation, Buffalo, NY). Reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction/Electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (RT-PCR/ESI-MS, Abbott Molecular, Des Plaines, IL) was performed for viral and bacterial pathogens using the Respiratory Virus Surveillance 2.5 kit and the Bacterial Antibiotic Candida kit. Both of these kits were purchased from Abbott Molecular. A positive detection was defined as a reaction found by RT-PCR/ESI-MS to have a Q score of more than 0.9.

Methods from the field of biostatistics

The major objective of our study was to determine the diagnostic accuracy of sonographically-confirmed clinical pneumonia in comparison to the gold standard of radiographically-confirmed clinical pneumonia. This comparison was carried out on pediatric study participants who had respiratory findings, had been given a diagnosis of clinical pneumonia by a study physician, and had both a CXR and a LUS performed as part of the research project. Only because asthma, bronchitis, and upper respiratory infections exhibited modest rates of consolidation on CXR did we decide to focus on clinical pneumonia. Positive sonographic results were defined by us as the detection of a consolidation or any abnormality on LUS. It was shown that there was a difference in diagnostic accuracy between consolidation and any abnormality on LUS, when compared to radiographically-confirmed clinical pneumonia. This was demonstrated by include any abnormality on LUS in the study. Positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), sensitivity, specificity, and the C-statistic as a measure of area under the Receiving Operator Characteristic curve were used to determine diagnostic accuracy. We investigated continuous variables by utilizing analysis of variance to determine their means, and we analyzed categorical variables by determining their proportions using chi-square tests or Fisher exact tests, depending on the circumstance. The kappa coefficient was utilized in order to ascertain the level of agreement that existed between the several readers. R (www.r-project.org) and STATA version 13 were the statistical programs that we used for our investigations (StatCorp, College Station, Texas).

Results

Characteristics of the Participants

1428 children were evaluated to determine their eligibility based on the results of the experiment (Fig. 1). 1062 (or 74 percent) of those children went through the LUS procedure. After the first evaluation, it was determined that 128 children were ineligible because of their age or the presence of a cardiac or chronic respiratory disease. Further evaluation revealed that 163 children who did not exhibit any respiratory symptoms actually suffered from an acute illness that was not related to the respiratory system. In addition, there were 76 ultrasounds that could not be performed because of time constraints or because the parents refused. 19 months was the median age, and 57% of the population was male. The following diagnoses were determined to be final in the clinical setting: 453 of the patients were diagnosed with clinical pneumonia, 133 had asthma, 103 were diagnosed with bronchiolitis, 143 were diagnosed with an upper respiratory infection, and 230 were children who did not have any respiratory symptoms (Table 2). CXR found abnormalities that were consistent with pneumonia in 360 of the children (79 percent), of which 191 (42 percent) had consolidations and 169 (37 percent) had an interstitial abnormality.

Table 2 summarizes the demographic data and clinical characteristics of each study group. In children younger than 12 months old, tachycardia was defined as a heart rate of more than 190 beats per minute, and in children older than 12 months old, tachycardia was defined as a heart rate of more than 140 beats per minute. For children aged 2–11 months,

tachypnea was defined as a respiratory rate of more than 50 breaths per minute, and for children aged 12 months, the definition was a respiratory rate of more than 40 breaths per minute.

Characteristics	Children without respiratory symptoms (n = 230)	Pneumonia (n = 453)	Asthma (n = 133)	Bronchiolitis (n = 103)	Upper respiratory infection (n = 143)	P Value
Demographic characteristics						
Age in months, mean (SD)	41.3 (15.2)	20.0 (14.6)	30.4 (18.2)	10.1 (10.1)	24.7 (16.9)	<0.001
Number < 12 months (%)	30 (13)	168 (37)	33 (25)	77 (75)	44 (31)	<0.001
Number of boys (%)	117 (51)	258 (57)	87 (65)	46 (35)	88 (62)	0.058
Clinical characteristics						
Symptoms, n (%)						
Cough	0 (0)	453 (100)	130 (98)	103 (100)	138 (97)	<0.001
Difficulty breathing	0 (0)	416 (92)	118 (89)	91 (88)	71 (50)	<0.001
Rhinorrhea	0 (0)	376 (83)	107 (80)	83 (81)	123 (86)	<0.001
Fever	0 (0)	348 (77)	69 (52)	57 (55)	55 (38)	<0.001
Diarrhea	0 (0)	96 (21)	19 (14)	23 (22)	16 (11)	<0.001
Chest indrawing, n (%)	0 (0)	203 (45)	48 (36)	48 (46)	1 (1)	<0.001
Temperature, mean (SD)	36.4 (0.4)	36.9 (0.7)	36.9 (0.6)	36.8 (0.6)	36.7 (0.6)	<0.001
Number with ≥ 38.0 °C (%)	1 (0)	48 (11)	9 (7)	8 (8)	8 (6)	<0.001
Heart Rate						
Infants, mean (SD)	122 (14)	138 (17)	127 (19)	135 (17)	133 (15)	
Children, mean (SD)	107 (10)	129 (18)	127 (17)	129 (18)	114 (16)	
Number with tachycardia (%)	3 (1)	89 (20)	22 (17)	7 (7)	8 (6)	<0.001
Respiratory Rate						
Infants, mean (SD)	29 (4)	45 (11)	46 (13)	44 (13)	35 (11)	
Children, mean (SD)	23 (3)	39 (11)	36 (11)	42 (13)	27 (6)	
Number with tachypnea (%)	1 (0)	203 (45)	43 (32)	42 (41)	13 (9)	<0.001
Oxyhemoglobin Saturation (SpO ₂) %, mean (SD)	99 (1)	96 (3)	96 (3)	97 (2)	99 (2)	
Number with SpO ₂ <95% (%)	1 (0)	47 (10)	18 (14)	7 (7)	1 (1)	

Inter-reader agreement

When it comes to LUS, the kappa coefficients for agreement among readers were as follows: 0.65 (95 percent confidence interval: 0.61–0.66) overall, 0.73 (0.70–0.74) for a normal lung ultrasound, 0.38 (0.27–0.41) for interstitial abnormalities, and 0.77 (0.75–0.78) for lung consolidation. The results of the medium and large consolidations produced a kappa coefficient of 0.87 (0.86–0.89), while the findings of the small consolidation produced a kappa coefficient of 0.77 (0.74–0.81). Regarding the CXR, the kappa coefficients for agreement among readers were as follows: 0.37 (95 percent confidence interval: 0.34–0.40) overall, 0.40 (0.37–0.42) for normal chest radiographs, 0.20 (0.16–0.23) for interstitial abnormalities, and 0.51 (0.48–0.58) for lung consolidation.

Characteristics of imaging systems

There were a total of 1062 ultrasounds that could be looked over. In children who did not have any respiratory symptoms, there was no consolidation of the lungs in any of them, but 11 (one percent) of them did have an interstitial abnormality. 414 (or fifty percent) of the 832 participants who were experiencing respiratory symptoms had a sonographic lung consolidation, and 530 (or sixty-four percent) of them had any abnormality (Table 3). It took less than ten minutes to perform LUS on average; 5.5 2.1 minutes in healthy controls, compared to 8.2 3.1 minutes in children with pneumonia ($p < 0.001$ for both comparisons). In Table 2, we have provided a summary of the characteristics of the LUS findings. There were a total of 832 CXRs that were open for inspection. 221 of these, or 26%, had lobar consolidations, while 264, or 32%, had interstitial abnormalities.

Fig2: An ultrasound picture of the lungs taken of a patient with community-acquired pneumonia. A significant lobar consolidation with uneven and serrated borders; the area of consolidation includes sonographic air bronchograms (arrows)

Table 3 Lung ultrasound diagnosis and characteristics.

Final ultrasound diagnosis	Children without Respiratory Symptoms (n = 230)	Pneumonia (n = 453)	Asthma (n = 133)	Bronchiolitis (n = 103)	Upper respiratory infection (n = 143)	P Value
Procedure time in minutes, mean (SD)	5.5 (2.1)	8.2 (3.1)	7.2 (2.5)	7.5 (2.6)	5.9 (4.2)	<0.001
Normal ultrasound, n (%)	219 (95)	93 (21)	67 (50)	36 (35)	107 (75)	<0.001
Large Consolidation	0 (0)	127 (28)	3 (2)	8 (8)	0 (0)	<0.001
Shred sign	0 (0)	24 (19)	0 (0)	2 (25)	0 (0)	0.81
Air Bronchogram	0 (0)					
Pleural Abnormalities	0 (0)	23 (18)	2 (67)	3 (38)	0 (0)	0.03
Pleural Effusion	0 (0)	22 (17)	1 (33)	1 (13)	0 (0)	0.64
Interstitial Findings	0 (0)					
Small Consolidation	0 (0)	175 (39)	46 (35)	41 (40)	15 (10)	<0.001
Shred sign	0 (0)	35 (20)	0 (0)	5 (12)	7 (47)	<0.001
Air Bronchogram	0 (0)					
Pleural Abnormalities	0 (0)	59 (34)	18 (19)	14 (34)	2 (13)	0.34
Pleural Effusion	0 (0)	1 (1)	1 (2)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0.60
Interstitial Findings	0 (0)					
Focal Interstitial syndrome	9 (4)	43 (9)	8 (6)	10 (10)	13 (9)	0.09
Diffuse Interstitial syndrome	1 (0)	9 (2)	5 (4)	6 (6)	4 (3)	0.02
Pleural abnormalities only	1 (0)	6 (1)	4 (3)	2 (2)	4 (3)	0.26

Diagnostic performance

When compared with radiographically confirmed clinical pneumonia, consolidation on lung ultrasound had a sensitivity of 88.5 percent, a specificity of 100 percent, and an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.94 (95 percent confidence interval: 0.92–0.97) (Table 4). When compared with radiographically confirmed clinical pneumonia, any abnormality on the lung ultrasound had a sensitivity of 92.2 percent, a specificity of 95.2 percent, and an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.94 (95 percent confidence interval [CI]: 0.91–0.96). (Table 5).

Table 4 provides definitions and values for the purpose of analyzing diagnostic Accuracy.

True positive	True negative	Test	Total population	True positive	True negative	False positive	False negative
Radiographically-confirmed clinical pneumonia	Children without Respiratory Symptoms	Consolidation on lung ultrasound	421	169	230	0	22
Radiographically-confirmed clinical pneumonia	Children without Respiratory Symptoms	Any abnormality on lung ultrasound	421	176	219	11	15

Laboratory findings

A summary of the differences in ancillary laboratory data was provided according to the final diagnosis status (Table 5). The highest levels of procalcitonin were found in children who were diagnosed with pneumonia. These levels provided support for our clinical definitions of pneumonia and bronchiolitis. When compared to other groups of children, those who had bronchiolitis had an increased risk of having respiratory syncytial virus isolated from a pharyngeal swab taken from their throat. Over half of all participants carried the streptococcus pneumoniae bacteria, and there was no discernible difference between the children who exhibited respiratory symptoms and those who did not. In terms of demographic factors like age and gender, there was no discernible difference between those with and those without ancillary laboratory data (data not shown).

	Children without respiratory symptoms	Pneumonia	Asthma	Bronchiolitis	Upper respiratory infection	P value
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Blood cell count

Sample size	54	138	54	49	66	
Hemoglobin (mg/dl), mean (SD)	10.9 (1.3)	10.6 (1.3)	10.8 (1.7)	10.8 (1.4)	10.7 (1.4)	0.79
Number with <11 mg/dL (%)	26 (49)	56 (41)	26 (48)	19 (39)	29 (44)	0.74
Platelets x 10 ³ /L, mean (SD)	420 (136)	414 (146)	405 (124)	460 (130)	421 (136)	0.28
White blood cells x 10 ³ /L, mean (SD)	11.9 (5.5)	11.7 (5.1)	13.8 (6.7)	13.0 (6.0)	13.1 (5.0)	0.08
Number with >17 x 10 ³ /L (%)	8 (15)	20 (15)	13 (24)	7 (15)	16 (25)	0.26

Throat swabs result

	Children without respiratory symptoms	Pneumonia	Asthma	Bronchiolitis	Upper respiratory infection	P value
Sample size	32	32	41	46	50	
Respiratory virus, n (%)						
Any positive virus	4 (13)	29 (35)	18 (44)	23 (50)	11 (22)	0.002
Viral etiology						
Respiratory Syncytial Virus	0 (0)	12 (18)	8 (26)	14 (38)	4 (9)	<0.001
Adenovirus	3 (10)	6 (10)	6 (21)	1 (4)	4 (9)	0.45
Parainfluenza 1-3	0 (0)	5 (9)	2 (8)	5 (18)	1 (3)	0.07
Metapneumovirus	1 (3)	5 (9)	1 (4)	2 (8)	1 (3)	0.77
Influenza virus	0 (0)	2 (4)	1 (4)	0 (0)	2 (5)	0.79
Coronavirus	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (8)	0 (0)	0.04
Bacteria and Candida						
Any positive	32 (100)	79 (96)	36 (88)	42 (91)	50 (100)	0.03
Microorganism etiology						
<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	18 (56)	52 (63)	27 (66)	30 (65)	33 (66)	0.91
<i>Candida albicans</i>	2 (6)	6 (7)	2 (5)	9 (20)	7 (14)	0.11
<i>Haemophilus influenzae</i>	1 (3)	6 (7)	0 (0)	2 (4)	2 (4)	0.45
<i>Moraxella catarrhalis</i>	1 (3)	2 (2)	0 (0)	1 (2)	1 (2)	0.89
<i>Neisseria meningitidis</i>	1 (3)	1 (1)	1 (2)	1 (2)	0 (0)	0.80
Procalcitonin, ng/ml						
Sample size	28	113	50	27	41	
Median (IQR)	0.01 (0.00–0.03)	0.14 (0.06–0.55)	0.06 (0.04–0.08)	0.06 (0.04–0.09)	0.06 (0.04–0.11)	<0.001
Geometric mean (95% CI)	0.03 (0.03–0.04)	0.19 (0.15–0.25)	0.07 (0.06–0.09)	0.07 (0.05–0.09)	0.08 (0.06–0.10)	<0.001

Discussion

Our research demonstrates that point-of-care lung ultrasonography is a viable and accurate approach for identifying radiographically verified clinical juvenile pneumonia. LUS required fewer than ten minutes on average to execute with

excellent inter-reader agreement. In addition, there is a strong correlation between LUS diagnosis of consolidation and radiographic confirmation of clinical pneumonia in children.

Two recent meta-analyses conducted by our lab confirmed the high accuracy of LUS for the diagnosis of pneumonia in adults [16] and children [17]; however, these analyses were hampered by small sample sizes and heterogeneity among studies, hence lowering the overall power. In addition, five of the eight studies focused on hospitalized or severely ill children [283032] or neonates [2931], limiting their applicability to outpatient or emergency department settings. In addition, sonographers were not blinded to clinical information because they reviewed the LUS at the time of clinical evaluation.

Our research has a number of merits and contributes fresh and significant information. We enrolled more than one thousand children under the age of five and conducted all testing in a busy tertiary hospital with limited resources, indicating that LUS may be realistically implemented in high-volume clinical settings without severe work disruptions. This study is the first to our knowledge to assess the reproducibility of LUS between several readers utilizing a standardized method for conducting LUS. We presented detailed descriptions of the sonographic results, distinguishing between small pleural anomalies and interstitial B-lines and big consolidations. In addition, we evaluated participants with a variety of respiratory diseases, including a group of youngsters without respiratory symptoms, using LUS. With the exception of Caiulo et al. [33] who also analyzed bronchiolitis, previous study concentrated exclusively on pneumonia and excluded healthy children and those with other respiratory disease processes. Although not part of the diagnostic reference standard, auxiliary laboratory testing increased our confidence in our diagnoses. Procalcitonin has been demonstrated to be higher in bacterial illness [34] and was highest in children with radiographically confirmed pneumonia compared to those who did not have pneumonia. Consistent with earlier epidemiological research [24], the proportion of children with respiratory syncytial virus was highest among those with bronchiolitis rather than pneumonia. However, there is a restriction to the use of pharyngeal swabs because the prevalence of *S. pneumoniae* did not differ between children with and without respiratory symptoms.

Our study may have some possible flaws. First, we did not do computed tomography (CT) scans on all children with respiratory symptoms, as the standard of care would not have recommended CT scans for diagnosing pneumonia in children. Despite its limitations, we utilized radiographically proven clinical pneumonia as our gold standard, which we think to be the safest alternative to the present gold-standard. As a result, we were unable to arbitrate differences in findings between LUS and CXR. LUS cannot detect consolidations that do not reach the pleura, whereas CXR cannot image minor consolidations (1 intercostal gap) identified on LUS [27]. However, the clinical significance of minor LUS consolidations remains unknown. In addition, retrocardiac opacifications or consolidations may be less visible on anteroposterior CXRs compared to LUS. Second, we lacked information on the duration and severity of the illness. In particular, we did not monitor the clinical course and simply performed imaging at the time of enrollment. Thirdly, it is possible that LUS cannot distinguish between mild alveolar anomalies and atelectasis. While Lichtenstein et al. [35] reported that dynamic air bronchograms are more likely to occur in pneumonia than in atelectasis in adults, detection of dynamic air bronchograms in children is challenging due to their smaller body size. Fourth, the overall diagnostic sensitivity of LUS for radiographically confirmed pneumonia was lower than previously reported [15,16]. This may be partially attributable to selection bias in prior research, in which participants were more likely to have severe

pneumonia. It could possibly be attributable to the location of the probes in our investigation; we did not regularly use transverse views, which could have increased the diagnostic yield in youngsters [17]. Fifth, the physician administering the ultrasound was not blinded to observable clinical symptoms, which may have caused him or her to spend more time performing LUS on children who appear sicker. Sixth, the kappa for CXR agreement in our study was lower than that of earlier research [36,34]. This may be attributable to a lack of adherence to the WHO standards for interpreting CXRs, low CXR quality, and the diversity of respiratory disease in our study cohort.

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